

Designing at 1:1 Scale on Wall-Sized Displays Using Existing UI Design Tools

Annex 2

Second user study documents: prototyping at 1:1 scale on WSD with Miro

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Introduction

This document is an annex to the paper “Designing at 1:1 Scale *on* Wall-Sized Displays Using Existing UI Design Tools” written by Lou Schwartz, Mohammad Ghoniem, Valérie Maquil, Adrien Coppens, and Johannes Hermen.

This document contains documents used to conduct the user study and its results. It is composed as follows:

1. Preparation task: the task given to participants before the user study to get familiar with Miro and the object types composing the mockup to reproduce.
2. Technical protocol.
3. Discussion guide: the guide for the facilitator to present the experimentation to participants and to collect their consent.
4. Task description: the mockup to reproduce during the user study.
5. Debriefing guide: the guide for the facilitator to collect the feedback of participants.
6. Mockups made by the participants: the result produced by each participant for each condition.

1. Preparation task

1. To discover Miro to design UI, you can use the following links:
 - Introduction <https://miro.com/research-and-design/ui/>
 - How to draw a shape <https://help.miro.com/hc/en-us/articles/360017730713-Shapes>
 - General short introduction video [EN-5min]: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UnPy3Fw-7WM>
 - Info, to draw a broken line:
 - o Use the form “line”
 - o Click on the middle blue point and move it

- o Then two blue points appear that you can also move, etc

2. Sign in to Miro: Sign in | Miro | The Visual Workspace for Innovation

3. Create a new blank board.
4. Try to design the following interface on your computer starting from scratch.

2. Technical protocol

2.1. Documents needed:

- For the first session signed consent forms (2 times) + Information notice
- Task documents
- Discussion guide
- IPAD + charger if needed

2.2. Immersive arena

2.3. Before a session

WSD-IA

1. Load the tablet + participant's tablet if needed
2. Switch on screens
3. Start computer of the WSD-IA
4. Start OBS PC
5. Start Miro
 - a. Select Miro on the control tablet
 - b. Log in
 - c. Open the right project
 - d. Check zoom in Chrome, should be 200%
 - e. Position the browser window (11 displays of 12, not use the left one on the door)
6. Install the table in the centre with the interaction device (keyboard or tablet) and the documents for the task
7. If tablet is used, connect the tablet to the same account & open the same project
8. If Touch is used turn on Touch ("touch ON" on the control tablet), otherwise switch it off ("touch OFF" on the control tablet).

WSD-VW

1. Load participant's tablet if needed
2. Let the technician start the WSD-VW
3. Start PC observer
4. Start Miro
 - a. Select Miro on the control tablet
 - b. Log in
 - c. Open the right project
 - d. Check zoom in Chrome, should be 200%
5. Install the table in the centre with the interaction device (keyboard or tablet) and the documents for the task.
6. If tablet is used, connect the tablet to the same account & open the same project

2.4. During the session

1. Input the ID of the OBS session on the control tablet
2. Start recording (OBS)
3. Manipulation by the participant

2.5. After the session

1. Stop the recording (OBS)
2. Screen shot of the WSD-IA display (FN+BACK)
3. If tablet is used, screen shot of the tablet display (POWER + middle button at the same time)
4. Input the ID of the OBS session on the control tablet: IDsession-debrief
5. Debriefing in the IA
6. Stop recording the debrief

3. Discussion guide

3.1. Welcome

3.2. Explanation of the purpose of the study

Thank you for participating in this study in the frame of the internal project PLayer2. The study consists of six sessions when you will be asked to reproduce a mock-up in real size directly on a wall-sized display using a specific interaction method.

The interface to reproduce consists in a control tower that supports experts and decision-makers in managing medical supply chains during COVID-19, where hospitals had difficulties obtaining the needed personal protective equipment (e.g., surgical masks, goggles, gowns) on time. The hospitals had to take care of all the tasks related to ordering new stock by themselves as the usual intermediary suppliers were no longer delivering.

You will reproduce the mock-up of the first task, where the team needs to estimate the upcoming new COVID-19 infections and hospital occupancy, based in part on information from social media.

So, you will play the role of the designer of this interface.

3.3. Consent form signature

Before to start, I will ask you to read this information concerning your right about the management of your data and sign the consent form in 2 copies, one for you and one for us.

We will record the study by video, take some photographs, capture your movements in the space and observe all your actions. Your data will be pseudonymised. And the capturing elements will be used for scientific dissemination.

If you have any questions, please ask them before you sign.

3.4. Explanation of the task and the steps of the study

You are a designer, and you would like to see in real size the result of a first mock-up designed for the wall-sized display presents here.

To do that, you will reproduce the mock-up on the WSD using MIRO, a web-based whiteboard.

You will interact

- With this **keyboard** and its trackpad.
- Using **touch** directly on the screens. If you need to input text or a numeric value, you can use the available keyboard.
- On this **tablet** that is synchronized. So, you will see all your modifications done on the tablet directly on the wall-sized display.

Please try to use **only** this interaction method.

You have one hour to reproduce as much as you can of this mock-up. You have here some zoomed views.

If you feel tired and want to stop, just inform me.

Please verbally comment on your actions as much as possible when designing.

A debriefing will be done when you are finished.

4. Task description

4.1. Interface to reproduce

Figure 1: overall view of the rendering on the immersive arena.

Figure 2: Print screen.

Figure 3: Screens cutting for WSD-IA.

Figure 4: Screens cutting for WSD-VW.

4.1. Close-up views

Tasks

This screen shows you the different tasks that you need to accomplish. Tap "next" when you would like to move to the next task.

→ **Task 1 : Estimate future COVID numbers**

Based on the news, estimate hospital and ICU occupancy for the next 3 months.

News

RTL today @RTLToday

● Luxembourg is in the middle of a new Omega wave. Latest projections from the Covid-19 Taskforce show that there will be a **peak** in September with 1200 new infections per day. Hospitalizations will reach up to 60 in normal care and up to 20 in ICU.

4:38 PM · Jul 28, 2024 · Twitter Web App

10k Retweets 8k Quote Tweets 899 Likes

World Health Organization (WHO) @WHO

BREAKING:
The WHO warns from a new variant of the coronavirus that seems to lead to more hospitalizations. It is more important than ever that you get your vaccination and booster as soon as possible #fight #COVID19.

4:50 PM · Jul 29, 2024 · Twitter Web App

104k Retweets 88k Quote Tweets 500k Likes

COVID Estimation

Here you can estimate hospital and ICU occupancy for the next three months. Move the sliders accordingly.

New infections per day

August 2024

September 2024

October 2024

Hospital occupancy per day

August 2024

September 2024

October 2024

ICU occupancy per day

August 2024

September 2024

October 2024

COVID Data

These graphs show you the current COVID numbers (blue) as well as the estimated ones (red) for the next three months.

New Infections

Hospital occupancy Luxembourg

ICU occupancy

Hospital occupancy (your hospital)

ICU occupancy (your hospital)

Attendees

This Screen shows the list of current Attendees.

5. Debriefing guide

Session ID = _____

Free spontaneous feedback

Sentence completion method

I will ask you to complete the following sentences.

- By system we mean designing on a wall-sized display using [this **keyboard / touch** directly on the screens / this **tablet**].

1. **My first impression when using this system was... [first impression]**

2. **Spending an hour on this system gives me the feeling of... [user experience]**

3. **On a daily basis, I can use this system to...? [utility]**

4. **The system is easy to use because... [usability]**

5. **The system would be easier to use if... [usability]**

6. **I would need this system to be... [needs]**

7. **In order for me to want to use this system, I would have to ... [expectations]**

Do you have any other comment or remark?

6. Mockups produced by the participants

in chronological order for each participant.

6.1. Participant 1

WSD-IA, keyboard

WSD-IA, tablet

WSD-IA, touch

WSD-WV, touch

WSD-WV, keyboard

WSD-WV, tablet

6.2. Participant 2

WSD-IA, tablet

WSD-IA, touch

WSD-IA, keyboard

WSD-WV, keyboard

WSD-WV, touch

WSD-WV, tablet

